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Review Article

A DETAILED REVIEW ON CAPSULES**¹Gandrathi Srujana¹, ²Dr. Chandrasekhara Rao Baru, ³Bonthala Veena,
⁴Jeenukunta Pravalika**¹Asst. Professor- Department of Pharmaceutics, ²Professor & Principal- Department of Pharmaceutics², ^{3,4} Students- Chilkur Balaji College of Pharmacy, Hyderabad, India**Abstract:**

The drug and the excipients are enclosed in either a soft or hard soluble shell. Generally, the capsules are the solid preparations. The Shell which is used for closing the drug are made of gelatin or the polymeric substances. The capsules are tasteless, odourless, elegant and easy to swallow. They are either soft capsules or hard capsules where the soft capsules possess a flexibility and plasticized gelatin film while the hard capsule composed of two pieces, the shorter piece called cap and longer piece called body.

Keywords: capsules, soft gelatin capsule, hard gelatin capsule, shell.

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INTRODUCTION:

Capsules are defined as unit solid dosage form of medicaments available as small containers made up of gelatin enclosing accurately measured drug substances.

Capsula is the Latin word which gives the term capsule which means small container.

Because of the manufacturing process compared to the other dosage forms the capsules are believed as the primary oral dosage form. The medicament is released when the gelatin comes in contact with the water as the gelatin has the disintegrating property.

The capsule shell can be made with the gelatin, denatured gelatin, methyl cellulose, Polyvinyl alcohol (1). Occasionally capsules may be administered rectally and vaginally. The medication can be powder or a liquid or semi solid mass (2).

History:

1830-Capsules were first patented by Joseph Gerard Auguste Dublanc and francois Achille which are made from soft gelatin.

1846 - two-piece hard capsules patented by Jules lehuby.

1931 - Aurthur Calton invented a machine that make hard capsules (3).

Advantages:

1. The appearance of capsule is neat & elegance.
2. Tasteless, odourless so easy administration.
3. The medication is released rapidly because of the solubility of gelatin at gastric pH.
4. Increases rate of release of the drug.
5. patient compliance.
6. Easily swallowed.
7. Rapid disintegration.
8. Rapid bioavailability.
9. capsules are smooth (4).

Disadvantages:

1. Not preferred for efflorescent or deliquescent materials.
- 2) Capsules are not suitable for liquids that dissolves gelatin.
- 3) The rapid release of materials such as very soluble salt like bromides, Iodides should not be dispensed in capsules (4).

Types of capsules:

There are two types of capsules and they are

1. Hard gelatin capsules.
2. soft gelatin capsules.

A. Hard Shell Capsule**Soft gelatin capsules:**

Developed in 19th century to mask unpleasant taste and odor of drug Substances. It has many applications for pharmaceutical, health and Cosmetic purposes (5)

A soft gel capsule is one piece containing a liquid, a suspension or semisolid referred to as fill. The rotary die process is involved for the preparation of soft gelatin capsules.

Generally, the soft gelatin capsules are made from gelatin. They are subdivided into two types:

- (a) soft gelatin capsules.
- (b) Non gelatin soft capsules (6).

The soft gelatin capsules are preferred for the strategic reasons, safety aspects and because of the consumer preferences (7).

The components involved in soft gelatin capsules are gelatin, preservative, colorants, and flavors.

Gelatin:

It is the basic component of the soft gelatin capsule. The gelatin is alkali processed which constitutes 40%

of the wet molten gel mass.

Plasticizing agent:

They are added to ensure the flexibility. These agents promote the retention or moisture. Eg: glycerol, sorbitol mannitol, polypropylene glycol.

Water:

The water is important in manufacturing process to ensure that capsule is flexible. It accounts for 30-40% of the wet gel formulation.

Preservatives:

They are used to prevent the growth of bacteria.

Eg: ethyl hydroxybenzoate, propyl hydroxybenzoate, methyl hydroxybenzoate, potassium sorbate.

Colorants and opacifier:

The darker color is preferred for the visual appeal and also reduces the penetration of Light for the encapsulation of a photosensitive drug.

Flavoring and sweetening agents:

They are used to improve the palatability. Polymers: They are used to impart enteric release and to formulate the chewable capsules. Chelating agents:

They are used to prevent chemical degradation of oxidation. Eg: EDTA (ethylene diamine tetrameric acid)(6)(8).

Hard gelatin capsules:

It is simple dosage form for oral drug delivery. This type of capsule consists of two pieces

(1) cap, (2) Body.

These capsules are generally cylindrical in shape (9), (10).

They contain only 12-16 % of moisture. The Capsules are filled with dry solids and they are powders, granules, pellets, Tablets (11).

Basic component of hard gelatin capsules:

Gelatin : It is the well-known material for the preparation of hard capsule shells. This material can be obtained from the skin, white connective tissue, bones of animals.

Plasticizer: They are used to reduce the rigidity of the polymer. Eg: glycerine, polyhydric alcohol.

Colorants, preservatives and opacifying agent, are also used as excipients in the hard gelatin capsules (12), (13).

Manufacturing of hard gelatin capsules:

steps involved:

Dipping, Spinning, drying, Stripping, Trimming, and joining, polishing. Dipping:

The stainless-steel pins are dipped into the Solution to form the capsule which includes the cap and the body. The temperature must be maintained at 50°C in a Jacketed dipping pan.

Spinning:

The pins are rotated for the uniform distribution of the gelatin to avoid the formation Of the bead at the end of the capsules.

Drying:

It is done to dry the gelatin with the air to form the shell. stripping:

To strip the cap and body portions from the pins.

Trimming & joining:

The cap and body are trimmed with the knives and later they are joined(14),(15).

Filling of hard gelatin capsules: various filling machines are available-

- Eli-lily and co
- Macofar SAS
- Farmatic
- Osaka
- Hofli ger

➤ parke-dare (15), (16).

Manufacturing of soft gelatin capsule:

It involves four methods:

1) plate process

- 2) Accogel machine
- 3) Rotary die process
- 4) Bubble method.

Rotary die process:

The gelatin sheets are feed on rolls contain small Orifice hinded up with the die pocket. The material flows with the gravity. The gelatin ribbons are fed with the paste between the rollers and the sealing is done by the mechanical pressure (17).

Plate process:

The plate contains the numerous die pockets where the gelatin sheet is placed. The sheet is drawn into the die pockets with the help of the vacuum. Then the pockets are filled with the liquid or the paste. The another

Sheet is used for placing them on the filled pockets and sandwiched under a die press (18).

Accogel machine:

It Involves mainly those parts -

- 1) Measuring you
- 2) Die roll
- 3) Sealing roll

The gelatin is transferred into the gelatin linked pocket with the help of measuring roll and die roll. Then the Second gelatin Sheet is applied to form the other half of the capsule. pressure between the die & Sealing roll cuts out the capsule (17).

Bubble method:

The molten gelatin is discharged into the outer annulus and liquid content from the tube. Then the liquid discharged into the chilled-oil of column as droplets from the concentric tube (19).

Evaluation test for capsules:

1) content uniformity test:

The amount of active ingredient should be within the range of 85% to 115% of the label amount for 9 of 10 capsules with no unit outside the range of 70% to 125% of label amount (20).

2) weight variation test:

The average weight of the 20 tablets are calculated after weighing each tablet. If the weight of the individual capsule falls within 90-110 % of the average weight then the test is passed (21).

3) Disintegration time test for capsules:

It is done to ensure that the drug Substance is fully

Size	Volume in ml	Size in mm
000	1.37	26.3
00	0.95	23.7
0	0.68	21.8
1	0.50	19.2
2	0.37	18.3
3	0.30	15.3
4	0.21	14.7
5	0.15	11.9

available for dissolution and absorption from the gastrointestinal tract. The Capsules taken in the basket rack assembly and lowered for 30 minutes into a thermostatically controlled bath of fluid at 37±2degrees celsius (5).

4) Shelf-life test:

test done after the storage at predetermined conditions. This test helps in verifying the shelf life & stability of the drug (22).

5) Dissolution test:

Take 1000ml of water at 36.5° into the vessel and add specified number of Capsules in basket and adjust the speed to 100rpm. Withdraw the required volume for every 10 minutes time interval. The Sample passes the test if the amount of Active ingredients in the solution is not less than 70% of the standard amount (23).

6) moisture permeation test:

The color change indicates the preserve of the moisture and the drug also gains the weight by absorbing the moisture (24).

Storage:

Hard gelatin capsules:

They should be stored at 24° to 28 degrees celsius. At high humidity they absorb moisture and lose its shape and at low humidity, they loss water and become brittle.

Soft gelatin Capsules:

Humidity does not exceed 45%RH at 21-24degrees celsius (25).

Stability:

It is done to determine the shelf life of capsule and to maintain the physical, chemical, microbiological, therapeutic, and toxicological identification right from the date of formulation and packaging until its therapeutic action (25).

Sizes of the capsules:

- The largest size of the capsule is No:000.
- The Smallest size of the capsule is No:5.
- The standard shape of capsule is traditional, Symmetrical and bullet shape(26).

FUTURE PERSPECTIVE:

Due to the rapid advances in capsule dosage form the hard gelatin capsules are more preferred.

- There will be more growth on the plant- based capsules as the people look for the quality & Lifestyle fit.
- As the rapid sealing technology is available, the capsules will be more preferred.
- Capsule manufacturers will continue to improve the materials, processes and related technologies to this versatile dosage form.

CONCLUSION:

Capsules are solid preparations in which drug substance and / or excipients are enclosed in either soft or hard soluble shell.

Depending upon the composition of the Capsule shell, the capsules are classified as hard or soft capsule. Capsules are filled with a range of formulation types like dry powders, semi solids, nonaqueous liquids and other dosage forms.

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